

Synthesis of some nitrogen mustards

Girish Kumar Sinha*, Bibhishan Pandey and Nityanand Singh

Department of Chemistry, Science College, Patna-800 005, India

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Several Mannich base nitrogen mustards have been synthesised by the condensation of 3-substituted-phthalimides and 4-substituted-phthalimides with *N*-bis(2-chloroethyl)amine in ethanol-formalin.

Mannich base nitrogen mustards are antineoplastic agents¹. Synthesis of nitrogen mustards derived from cyclohexanone and a variety of acetophenone employing a Mannich reaction between the respective ketones, formaldehyde and *N,N*-bis(2-chloroethyl)amine, has been reported¹. A number of amides and nitrogen heterocycles containing a labile N-H bond have been condensed with formaldehyde and a primary or secondary amine². Considering the reactivity of this labile N-H bond, the Mannich base nitrogen mustards have been synthesised from phthalimide, saccharin, isatin and isatin thiosemicarbazone with *N*-bis(β -chloroethyl)amine in ethanol-formalin (37% solution)³.

Substituted phthalimides were synthesised from 3-nitrophthalic acid and 4-nitrophthalic acid. These were heated with ammonium carbonate to produce the corresponding nitrophthalimides (**1a,d**) which were converted to aminophthalimides (**1b,e**) by reduction with stannous chloride and conc. HCl. Further, chlorophthalimides (**1c,f**) were prepared by diazotising aminophthalimides followed by treatment with cuprous chloride applying Sandmeyer's reaction. *N*-Bis(β -chloroethyl)amine hydrochloride was obtained by chlorinating diethanolamine with thionyl chloride⁴. The above Mannich reactions were carried out in a neutral solvent composed of ethanol and formalin. Condensation was essentially complete within a few minutes at ice-bath temperature but often the reaction periods were

one or more hours at room temperature.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 137G spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A 60D instrument using TMS as internal standard

N-Bis(2-chloroethyl)amine hydrochloride was prepared by refluxing a mixture of thionyl chloride (65 ml) and diethanolamine (25 g) in chloroform for 0.5 h and the resulting solid was crystallised from absolute ethanol and ether, m.p. 216–17°.

3-Nitrophthalimide (1a) and 4-nitrophthalimide (1d) . A mixture of nitrophthalic acid (21.2 g, 0.1 mol) and ammonium carbonate (12 g, 0.125 mol) was heated at 220–30° with occasional stirring for 1 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from water as cream coloured square plates : **1a**, m.p. 216–17°; **1d**, 196–97°.

3-Aminophthalimide (1b) and 4-aminophthalimide (1e) : Nitrophthalimide (20 g, 0.1 mol) was stirred with a solution of stannous chloride (84 g, 0.11 mol) in HCl (450 ml) and water (150 ml). The resulting solid was collected at 0°, washed with hot water and crystallised as yellow needles : **1b**, m.p. 264° d; **1e**, 294–95°.

3-Chlorophthalimide (1c) and 4-chlorophthalimide (1f) . Aminophthalimide (10 g, 0.1 mol) was added to a mixture of HCl (100 ml) and water (100 ml), then diazotised at 0–3° and added rapidly to freshly precipitated cuprous chloride, stirred for 3 h and the reaction mixture was warmed on a water-bath. The resulting solid was crystallised from acetic acid : **1c**, m.p. 235°; **1f**, 209–10°.

***N*-Bis(2-chloroethyl)aminomethylene-substituted-phthalimides (2a-f)** : Bis(2-chloroethyl)aminohydrochloride (1.1 g, 0.006 mol) was added to a cold solution of NaOH (0.3 g) in water (3 ml). The resulting bis(2-chloro-ethyl)amine was extracted with ether. The combined ether extracts was washed with ice-water and dried over fused MgSO₄, and concentrated under reduced pressure at ice-bath temperature. Compounds **1a-f** (0.006 mol) was then added to a cold ice-bath solution of the oily residue in 3 : 1 ethanol-for-

Note

malin (37%; 4 ml). After warming to 35–40° for several minutes in order to complete dissolution of phthalimide, the solution was maintained at room temperature for 1–4 h. The mixture was then cooled and the resulting white solid was crystallised from ethanol-ether : **2a**, m.p. 128–29°, ν_{\max} 1782, 1721 (C=O), 1448 (CH bend), 1545, 1365 (NO₂), 730 (C-Cl), δ 2.3 (2H, s, N-CH₂-N), 3.4–3.6 (8H, m, 2 × CH₂CH₂), 7.2–7.4 (3H, s, ArH); **b**, 84–85°, ν_{\max} 1760, 1700 (C=O), 1450 (CH bend), 3390 (NH), 750 (C-Cl), 2.4 (2H, s, N-CH₂-N), 3.5–3.6 (10H, m, 2 × CH₂CH₂, NH₂), 7.2–7.3 (3H, s, ArH); **c**, 178–79°, ν_{\max} 1780, 1720 (C=O), 1442 (CH bend), 750 (C-Cl), δ 2.3–2.4 (2H, s, N-CH₂-N), 3.4–3.5 (8H, m, 2 × CH₂CH₂), 7.1–7.4 (3H, s, ArH); **d**, 84–85°, ν_{\max} 1780, 1710 (C=O), 1530 (NO₂), 1455 (CH bend), 720 (C-Cl), δ 2.5 (2H, s, N-CH₂-N), 3.5–

3.6 (8H, m, 2 × CH₂CH₂), 7.4–7.5 (3H, s, ArH); **e**, 130–31°, ν_{\max} 1700 (C=O), 3390 (NH), 1440 (CH bend), 741 (C-Cl), δ 2.4–2.5 (3H, s, N-CH₂-N), 3.5–3.6 (10H, m, 2 × CH₂CH₂, NH₂), 7.1–7.3 (3H, s, ArH); **f**, 91–92°, ν_{\max} 1785, 1710 (C=O), 1430 (CH bend), 740 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl), δ 2.3–2.4 (2H, s, N-CH₂-N), 3.4–3.6 (8H, m, 2 × CH₂CH₂).

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